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UZBEK TAGSET: CREATING A LIST OF MORPHOLOGICAL AND SYNTACTIC TAGS FOR BUILDING MACHINE LEARNING MODELS FOR THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Abstract. The aim of this study is to develop a comprehensive list of syntactic and morphological tags in Uzbek, which aims to create a dataset for natural language processing (NLP) problems in Uzbek. The study involves a systematic analysis of Uzbek grammar, morphology, and syntax, and aims to identify and classify relevant linguistic features. Based on existing tagset models for other languages and taking into account the specific features of the Uzbek language, we propose a hierarchical tagset structure that includes word classes, morphological features, and syntactic functions. A Hidden Markov Model (HMM) was built to solve the POS tagging NLP task using the created tagset.

Key words: Uzbek language, syntactic tags, morphological tags, natural language processing, part of speech. HMM model

Introduction. The Uzbek language, a member of the Turkic language family, is spoken by over 30 million people, primarily in Uzbekistan, and has a rich history of linguistic development. Despite its significance in Central Asia, the computational processing of Uzbek remains underexplored, especially when compared to more widely studied languages. In the context of natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning (ML), the ability to effectively analyze and understand the syntactic and morphological structure of a language is crucial for tasks such as part-of-speech tagging, syntactic parsing, and machine translation. The issue of creating a tagged corpus is a key issue in natural language processing (NLP). The process of tagging texts means marking sentences, phrases, and words using tags taken from a predefined set of symbols (tags). Syntactic, morphological, and semantically tagged text is created by assigning syntactic, morphological, and semantic tags to each word or set of words in a sentence.

Sentences and words in the tagged text are enriched with grammatical marks.

Literature review. Previous studies on agglutinative languages highlight the complexities of POS tagging due to their rich morphological structures. Research on Uzbek has focused on developing morphological analyzers and tagsets to address these challenges, emphasizing their importance in NLP applications such as stemming, lemmatization, and syntactic parsing. The article highlights the integration of linguistics with digital technologies, focusing on the importance and methods of part-of-speech tagging in text analysis [1]. This paper presents a rule-based algorithm for punctuation analysis of periods and commas in Uzbek texts, which could also be applied to other Turkic languages and enhanced with machine learning in the future [2]. This paper explores using the SENNA neural network and word embeddings, trained on Wikipedia 2016 and METU corpora, for POS tagging. It evaluates word embeddings based on

semantic similarity and their performance in POS tagging with the PARDER tool [3]. This paper presents a Russian tagset based on the MULTEXT-East framework, containing about 600 tags. It achieves 95% accuracy on the Russian National Corpus, with a test set of tagging models and corpora provided for shared use [4]. POS tagging assigns labels to words in a sentence and is essential for NLP tasks. While taggers exist for languages like Hindi and Bengali, they use different tag sets. This paper discusses advancements in POS taggers for Indian languages and their importance in NLP [5]. This paper introduces a universal 12-category POS tagset and a mapping from 25 treebank tagsets, covering 22 languages. It demonstrates the resource's effectiveness in unsupervised grammar induction with competitive accuracy [6]. This paper presents InterSet, a universal approach for converting POS and morphological tags between corpora, addressing challenges in overlapping categories and proposing solutions for unification [7]. This paper develops a rule-based POS tagger for English using Lex and Yacc. The tagger applies a small set of rules and a limited dictionary to assign parts of speech to words based on their definitions and relationships with adjacent words [8]. This paper introduces a rule-based approach for detecting verbs in Uzbek, achieving an F1-score of 0.97, and surpassing current methods by utilizing affix-based morphological patterns [9]. This study proposes a method for improving POS tagging in agglutinative languages using character n-grams and multi-head attention. Tested on Uyghur, Uzbek, Kyrgyz, and Turkish datasets, the approach achieves accuracy improvements of 5.36% for Uyghur, 4.13% for Uzbek, and 2.1% for Kyrgyz [10].

Methodology. For the creation of artificial intelligence models that perform syntactic and morphological analysis and editing of Uzbek language texts, large-scale datasets are required. The task of creating such datasets can be addressed by building a tagged Uzbek language corpus. However, to date, there have been no tagged corpora specifically designed for training machine learning models in the Uzbek

language, and these are not available for public access on the internet.

In the process of creating a syntactic and morphological tagset for the Uzbek language, the following key recommendations are essential to ensure the effectiveness and accuracy of the developed resources. These recommendations focus on the importance of collaboration, leveraging existing resources, and involving the broader community to improve the overall outcome of the project.

- **Collaboration with Linguists.** Given the complexity of Uzbek's morphological and syntactic features, collaboration with native linguists and language experts is crucial at every stage of the process. Linguists will play an essential role in ensuring that the tagset is linguistically sound, reflecting the true nature of the language's structures. Their expertise will help identify nuanced grammatical patterns, including inflectional forms, syntactic dependencies, and rare constructions, which are vital for an accurate and comprehensive tagset. Moreover, their input is key in maintaining consistency across the corpus annotation process, making sure that the linguistic data is robust and reliable, and that it reflects the natural variation within the language, including regional dialects and spoken forms.
- **Leveraging Existing Resources.** While the Uzbek language is under-resourced in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP), there are valuable tools and datasets available for other Turkic languages, such as Turkish and Kazakh. Leveraging these existing resources can provide a useful starting point for building the Uzbek tagset. Many of these languages share common features in terms of agglutination, word formation, and syntactic structures, allowing for cross-linguistic insights and adaptations. Additionally, applying cross-lingual transfer learning techniques can be beneficial. This approach allows models trained on well-resourced languages to be fine-tuned for Uzbek, compensating for the smaller size of

the available corpus. By transferring knowledge from other languages, the performance of models on Uzbek data can be significantly improved, especially in the initial stages of development.

The paper discusses the development of morphological and syntactic tags for the Uzbek language. Morphological analysis and editing of texts are fundamental tasks in NLP making it essential to enrich texts with morphological features. Morphological tags (labels) are developed based on part-of-speech categories. Tags that encompass all the characteristics of nouns in the text were created as follows:

Table 1. List of tags for the noun.

№	Tag (label name)	Meaning	Examples
1	BOT	Birlik ot (Singular Noun)	<i>Mashina, kitob, olma</i>
2	KOT	Ko'plik otlar (Plural Nouns)	<i>Mashinalar, kitoblar</i>
3	SOT	Shaxs oti (Proper Nouns)	<i>O'qituvchi, duradgor</i>
4	NOT	Narsa oti (Concrete Nouns)	<i>Sumka, temir, atir</i>
5	JOT	Joy oti (Place Nouns)	<i>Qishloq, darvo</i>
6	FOT	Faoliyat-jarayon otlari (Action Nouns)	<i>Bazm, o'tirish, terim</i>
7	MOT	Mavhum otlar (Abstract Nouns)	<i>Sevgi, hayo</i>
8	POT	Payt oti (Time Nouns)	<i>Soniya, bahor, daqiqa</i>
9	SOOT	Sodda ot (Simple Nouns)	<i>Bino, bog'dorchilik</i>
10	QOT	Qo'shma ot (Compound Nouns)	<i>Markaziy Osivo</i>
11	JFOT	Juft oti (Dual Nouns)	<i>Uy-joy</i>
12	TOT	Takroriy ot (Repetitive Nouns)	<i>Tomir-tomiriga</i>
13	ATSH	Atoqli shaxs nomi (Personal Name)	<i>Akrom</i>
14	ATK	Kitob, asarlar nomi (Book/Work Name)	<i>"Shaytanat"</i>
15	ATT	Tashkilot nomi (Organization Name)	<i>"Uztransgaz"</i>
16	ATG	Joy nomi (Geographical Place)	<i>Yevropa</i>
17	ATH	Hayvon nomi (Animal Name)	<i>Olapar</i>
18	ATY	Yulduz, sayyora nomi (Star/Planet Name)	<i>Merkuriy</i>
19	ATM	Mahsulot nomi (Product Name)	<i>Snikers</i>
20	ATU	Unvon, medal nomi (Title/Medal Name)	<i>"Mard o'g'lon"</i>
21	ATNT	Muhim tarixiy sana nomi (Historical Date)	<i>Mustaqillik kuni</i>
22	ATI	Ilohiy tushuncha nomi (Divine Concept)	<i>Alloh</i>
23	ABR	Qisqartma otlar (Abbreviations)	<i>BMT, UNESCO</i>

The tagset is a foundational resource for developing machine learning models for the Uzbek language. The categorization of nouns, along with the inclusion of proper nouns, compound forms, and other lexical categories, enables more nuanced and accurate language processing. These tags will support various NLP tasks such as syntactic analysis, named entity recognition, and other applications that require understanding of the morphological and syntactic structure of the Uzbek language.

In the table above, we will look at tagging texts using the tags we developed. *BOT* – used to designate words in the singular noun phrase. Example: *Telefon/BOT yaxshi ekan*. Here, we used the BOT tag because the word “telefon” (phone) is a singular noun. We use the KOT tag to tag plural nouns in texts. Example: *Telefonlar/NOT/KOT ishlatilmaydi!* Here, since the word “telefonlar” (phones) is a noun and a plural noun, the NOT and KOT tags are set sequentially. *SOT* – Used to indicate a relative pronoun in texts. Example: *Rektor/SOT/BOT darsga keldi*. Here, since the word “rektor” (rector) is a personal noun and a singular noun, the SOT and BOT tags are used sequentially.

Table 2. List of tags for the verb.

№	Tag (label name)	Meaning	Examples
1	SIFL	Fe'lining sifatdosh shakli (Verb's Adjective Form)	<i>Borgan, ko'rgan, avtgan</i>
2	RFL	Fe'lining ravishdosh shakli (Verb's Adverbial Form)	<i>Borib, ko'rgach, avtgani</i>
3	HFL	Fe'lining harakat nomi shakli (Verb's Nominal Form)	<i>Borish, aytish, gapirmoq</i>
4	SFL	Sof fe'l shakli (Bare Verb Form)	<i>Ayt, o'qi, yugur</i>
5	SDFL	Sodda fe'l (Simple Verb)	<i>Gapirdi, eshildi</i>
6	QFL	Qo'shma fe'l (Compound Verb)	<i>E'lon qildi</i>
7	JFL	Juft fe'l (Dual Verb)	<i>Aytdi-tashladi</i>
8	TFL	Takroriy fe'l (Repetitive Verb)	<i>Qilasan-qilasan</i>
9	KFSQ	Ko'makch fe'lli so'z qo'shilmasi (kfsq) (Complex Verb with Auxiliary)	<i>Tashlab yubordi, o'qib chiqdi</i>
10	KOFL	Ko'makchi fe'l (Auxiliary Verb)	<i>Edi, emish, ekan</i>
11	1B	Birinchi shaxs, birlik (1st Person Singular)	<i>Bordim, boraman, kitobim</i>
12	2B	Ikkinchi shaxs, birlik (2nd Person Singular)	<i>Bording, boryapsan</i>
13	3B	Uchinchi shaxs, birlik (3rd Person Singular)	<i>O'qidi, bormoqchi</i>
14	1K	Birinchi shaxs, ko'plik (1st Person Plural)	<i>Sakradik, so'ramoqchimiz</i>
15	2K	Ikkinchi shaxs, ko'plik (2nd Person Plural)	<i>O'yladingiz, bormoqchisiz</i>
16	3K	Uchinchi shaxs, ko'plik (3rd Person Plural)	<i>Aytdilar, kitoblari</i>
17	OTZ	O'tgan zamon (Past Tense)	<i>Bordi, avtgan</i>
18	HOZ	Hozirgi zamon (Present Tense)	<i>Boryapti, ketmoqda</i>
19	KEZ	Kelasi zamon (Future Tense)	<i>Oladi, avtmoqchi</i>
20	TLF	To'liqsiz fe'l (Incomplete Verb)	<i>Edi, emish, ekan, emas</i>
21	BOG	Bog'lama (Linking Verb)	<i>Bo'lmoq, hisoblanmoq</i>

In Uzbek language processing, verbs play a crucial role in sentence construction and meaning. To facilitate machine learning model development for Uzbek, a well-defined tagset for verbs is essential. This tagset will help to distinguish between various verb forms, tenses, and syntactic roles, allowing for more effective processing of verb structures in NLP applications. Below is an outline of verb-related tags designed to capture the morphological and syntactic features of Uzbek verbs.

In addition to the detailed tagsets for nouns and verbs, similar tagsets have been developed for all other word classes in Uzbek. These include adjectives, pronouns, adverbs, prepositions, conjunctions,

interjections, numerals, particles, and determiners. Each tagset captures the specific morphological and syntactic features of these word classes, allowing for comprehensive analysis and processing of Uzbek in machine learning models. This complete tagging system supports a wide range of NLP tasks, ensuring that all aspects of the language can be accurately processed.

Results. The complete set of tagsets for Uzbek language word classes, including those for nouns, verbs, adjectives, pronouns, adverbs, and other parts of speech, has been uploaded to a dedicated GitHub repository

[<https://github.com/MaksudSharipov/UzbekTagSet>].

This repository serves as a centralized resource for researchers, developers, and linguists working on Uzbek language processing. By providing open access to these tagsets, the GitHub repository enables the broader community to use, adapt, and build upon this work for a variety of NLP tasks, such as part-of-speech tagging, syntactic parsing, and machine learning model development.

The repository is regularly updated and includes comprehensive documentation on how to use the tagsets, as well as examples and guidelines for integrating them into NLP workflows. Users can easily download the data, contribute to its improvement, or use it as a reference for their own research and applications. This initiative is part of the broader effort to enhance resources for the Uzbek language in the field of computational linguistics.

Table 3. Distribution of tags by part-of-speeches.

№	Part-of-speeches	Number of tags
1	Ot (Noun)	23
2	Sifat (Adjective)	10
3	Son (Number)	11
4	Olmosh (Pronoun)	11
5	Ravish (Adverb)	10
6	Fe'l (Verb)	21
7	Bog'lovchi (Conjunction)	8
8	Yuklama (Particle)	6

9	Ko'makchi (Auxiliary)	2
10	Modal (Modal)	12
11	Undov (Interjection)	3
12	Taqlid (Imitation)	2
Total		119

The two tables [Table-3 and Table-4] presented below provide an overview of the morphological tags and syntactic tags for Uzbek language processing. These tags are essential for comprehensive part-of-speech tagging and syntactic analysis, enabling more accurate language processing in machine learning and natural language processing (NLP) tasks.

Table 4. List of syntactic tags.

№	Syntactic Tag (label) name	Meaning
1	EG	Subject (Ega)
2	OK	Noun Predicate (Ot kesim)
3	FK	Verb Predicate (Fe'l kesim)
4	QA	Object (Qaratqich aniqlovchi)
5	SA	Adjective Modifier (Sifatlovchi aniqlovchi)
6	IA	Explanatory Modifier (Izohlovchi aniqlovchi)
7	VL	Verbal Complement (Vositali to'ldiruvchi)
8	VS	Direct Complement (Vositasiz to'ldiruvchi)
9	VH	Circumstantial (Vaziyat holi)
10	OH	Locative (O'rin holi)
11	PH	Temporal (Payt holi)
12	MH	Purpose (Maqsad holi)
13	DH	Degree/Quantity (Daraja-miqdor holi)
14	SAH	Causal (Sabab holi)
15	UN	Exclamation (Undalma)
16	KR	Insertion (Kiritma)

Together, these morphological and syntactic tagsets provide a comprehensive framework for processing the Uzbek language. By classifying words

both morphologically and syntactically, these tags enable more precise linguistic analysis, which is essential for tasks such as part-of-speech tagging, syntactic parsing, and machine learning model development for Uzbek. The total of 119 morphological tags and 16 syntactic tags ensure that a wide range of linguistic features are captured, providing a strong foundation for advanced NLP applications.

Using the tags developed above, it is possible to develop datasets used for syntactic and morphological processing of Uzbek texts and building machine learning models. Example:

- a) *Xayriyat/QML, qo'shning/SOT/BOT uyidan/JOT/BOT kechadan/POT/BOT buyon/VK chiqayotgan/SIFL taqir-tuqir/TT ovoz/NOT to'xtab+qoldi/SFL, lekin/ZBG tashqaridagi/JOT chumchuqlarning/NOT/BOT chirillashidan/HFL bezor+bo'lib/RFL baribir/HRV uxlay+olmadim/SFL/KFSQ."*
- b) *Avvalo/TRML, barchamiz/BOL ushbu/KOL yurtning/JOT/BOT farzandimiz/SOT/BOT, shu+sababdan/VK ona/XSF tuproqqa/NOT/BOT sadoqat/FOT tuyg'usini/NOT aslo/IYK unutmasligimiz+lozim/HFL",- dedi /SFL universitetimizning/JOT/BOT faxrli/XSF professori/SOT A.Anvarov/ATSH o'zining/OZOL BMTdagi/ATT yakunlovchi/XSF nutqida/NOT/BOT.*

Now, below, we present the same sentences syntactically tagged using the tags developed from Table 4:

- a) *Xayriyat/KR, qo'shning/QA uyidan/OH kechadan+buyon/PH chiqayotgan/SA taqir-tuqir/SA ovoz/EG to'xtab+qoldi/FK, lekin tashqaridagi/SA chumchuqlarning/QA chirillashidan/VL bezor+bo'lib/VH baribir/VH uxlay+olmadim/FK"*
- b) *Avvalo/KR, barchamiz/EG ushbu/SA yurtning/QA farzandimiz/OK, shu sababdan/SAH ona/SA tuproqqa/VL sadoqat/SA tuyg'usini/VS aslo unutmasligimiz lozim/OK",-dedi/FK universitetimizning/QA*

faxrli/SA professori/IA A.Anvarov/EG o'zining/QA BMTdagi/SA yakunlovchi/SA nutqida/OK.

Large datasets can be created using a list of tags developed for the Uzbek language.

HMM in NLP. The Hidden Markov model (HMM) is a probabilistic model used to describe or determine the probabilistic properties of a random process. The primary objective of an HMM is to understand a Markov chain by observing its hidden states. Hidden Markov model considers both observed states (words that we see in the input) and hidden states (part of speech tags). When we are doing POS tagging, our goal is to discover the sequence of tags S as given in Eq. 1.

$$S = \arg \max_S^{\arg \max} p(S|W) \quad (1)$$

Here, we find the sequence of POS tags with the highest probability given on a sequence of words. As tag emissions are overlooked in HMM, Bayes' rule is applied to change the probability into an equation as given below,

$$S = \arg \max_S p(S|w) = \arg \max_S \frac{p(w|S) p(S)}{p(W)} = \arg \max_S p(W|S) p(S) \quad (2)$$

Here $p(W)$ is a constant. Any changes in the sequence S will not change the probability $P(W)$. Hence eliminating it will not make any variation in the final sequence S which maximizes the probability. POS tagging is an essential step in text preprocessing for NLP, as NLP involves enabling machines to communicate with humans or other machines. We can consider HMM as a stochastic method for POS tagging. To clarify how HMM aids in selecting the correct POS tag for a sentence. Consider the sentence "Otabek a'lochi talaba" where "Otabek" is a noun, "a'lochi" is an adjective, and "talaba" is also a noun. The probability of a word belonging to a specific part of speech class is referred to as the Emission probability.

Let's look at an example:

- Otabek a'lochi talaba (*Otabek is an excellent student*)

- Sarvar Otabekni maqtadi (*Sarvar praised Otabek*)
- Sarvar va Otabek talabalar (*Sarvar and Otabek are students*).

The table below is a counting tableau showing the words along with their respective part of speech types:

Words	Noun	Verb	Adjective
Otabek	3	0	0
Sarvar	2	0	0
a'lochi	0	0	1
talaba	1	0	0
talabalar	1	0	0
maqtadi	0	1	0
va	0	0	0

Let's calculate the frequency of each word by dividing its occurrence by the total number of each part of speech in the set of sentences.

Words	Noun	Verb	Adjective
Otabek	3/7	0	0
Sarvar	2/7	0	0
a'lochi	0	0	1/1
talaba	1/7	0	0
talabalar	1/7	0	0
maqtadi	0	1/1	0
va	0	0	0

Now, we can create a table for the above set of sentences based on the sequence of their part of speech:

	Noun	Verb	Adjective	End
Start	3	0	0	0
Noun	1	1	1	0
Verb	0	0	0	1
Adjective	1	0	0	0

In the table, we now need to examine the combinations of parts of speech to calculate the transition probabilities.

	Noun	Verb	Adjective	End
Start	3/3	0	0	0
Noun	1/3	1/3	1/3	0
Verb	0	0	0	1/1

Adjective	1/1	0	0	0
e				

The values in the table above represent the corresponding transition probabilities for the given set of sentences.

In the above image, the vertical lines display the emission probabilities of the words in the sentence, while the horizontal lines represent the transition probabilities.

Conclusions. The development of a comprehensive morphological and syntactic tagset for the Uzbek language marks a significant milestone in the advancement of NLP for underrepresented languages. This study provides a structured framework that encapsulates the unique linguistic features of Uzbek, enabling precise part-of-speech tagging and syntactic parsing. By leveraging collaborations with linguists, cross-lingual transfer techniques, and insights from related Turkic languages, the tagset addresses the challenges posed by the rich morphological structure of Uzbek.

The 119 morphological tags and 16 syntactic tags developed in this work cover a broad spectrum of linguistic elements, from nouns and verbs to conjunctions and particles. This extensive categorization ensures adaptability for various NLP applications such as machine translation, syntactic parsing, and semantic analysis. The openly accessible repository not only promotes community engagement but also serves as a resource for researchers to enhance and expand this foundational work.

Future directions include extending this tagset for regional dialects, integrating semantic tagging, and developing machine learning models that effectively utilize this resource. The outcomes of this research underscore the importance of tailored linguistic resources in promoting computational applications for lesser-resourced languages.

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